

VALKYRIES

D2.9 Harmonization framework M24

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1. Executive Summary

WP2 provides the design, specifications, and requirements that need to be taken into account throughout the project life cycle. This includes an in-depth review of system requirements, outcomes from consultations with stakeholders, and pre-standardization research.

The Deliverable 2.9 *Harmonization framework* presents the results over the methodology for agile harmonization and standardization based in all information analysed. This deliverable is the second harmonization framework and represents the final framework at the end of the project.

The harmonization and standardization process is a multidisciplinary process where cross-sectoral experts with heterogeneous knowledge shall contribute, providing support in multiple initiatives, such as literature identification, specific procedures (and their differences between regions/countries), evaluation and information exchange.

This deliverable is an update of the previously submitted document D2.5 - Harmonization framework. The new content with respect to the last version submitted has been highlighted in yellow for easy review.

This deliverable D2.9 "Harmonisation framework" expose the methodology followed in the project, the tasks elaborated to select the priorities and the pre-harmonisation in these points. Neither partial nor final results are shown. The results are part of the deliverable D2.12 "Harmonization and Standardization Reports".

2. Identification

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3. Introduction

Since the beginning of time, natural and man-made events have caused innumerable victims, damage to the environment, and the economy that disturb the life of the society where it impacts. With technological evolution, a threat has been added to the historical ones, generating an increase in risks. This makes it necessary to generate a greater and better environment of security and protection for the entire society. This translates into carrying out actions executed in a planned and collaborative manner among all the agents involved to minimize the impact, especially the social and psychological impact, as well as reducing the vulnerability of the community to the consequences of disasters through the Disaster Management Lifecycle: Mitigation, Preparedness, Response, Recovery, and Toward Disaster Resilience.

Figure 1 - Valkyries global vision

Faced with these needs, the European Commission (EC) as a supranational figure has established structures to develop Pan-European resilience against disasters.

- Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre (DRMKC)¹
 - This tool integrates existing scientific interdisciplinary knowledge and co-develops innovative solutions according to needs. The activities developed translate and analyse complex scientific data.
 - INFORM. Collaboration of the Inter-Agency Standing Committee Reference Group on Risk, Early Warning and Preparedness and the European Commission.

¹ [Home - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/)

- Risk Data Hub. Web platform of European wide risk data and methodologies for Disaster Risk Assessment.
- DRM Networks.
- Social Media-Driven Disaster Risk Management (SMDRM). Identify, understand, and address the challenges for improving adoption of non-traditional social media data for disaster management by taking a collaborative approach between researchers and practitioners in disaster management to co-design solutions.
- Global Conflict Risk Index (GCRI). Expresses the statistical risk of violent conflict in a given country in the coming 1-4 years and is exclusively based on quantitative indicators from open sources.
- Epidemic Intelligence from Open Sources (EIOS). A unified, multidisciplinary approach to early detection, assessment and communication of public health risk using publicly available information.
- Unión Civil Protection Knowledge Network². Based on three principles or pillars: Partnership, Knowledge and Innovation. Partnership serves as a portal that promotes the transfer of knowledge and technology through scientific networks. Knowledge acquired by the lessons learned and exercises for the improvement of the results as scientific methods. Innovation composed of learning, development and verification through tests and trials.
 - Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEM). Information for emergency response and disaster risk management.
 - Union Civil Protection Mechanisms (UCPM).

The European framework presents special interest in the great risks at the border and those of low risk and great impact. These tools help in risk management and a response developed under the responsibility of the Member States (MS) that supports a joint response strategy.

Valkyries explores and analyses current and cutting-edge technologies, standards and regulations that have an impact on emergency management in border locations and that support the collaboration of security forces and volunteers from the countries involved and within the European Community. Based on this objective, methodologies, adaptation tactics and criteria are developed for the harmonization of Pan-European systems. The solutions that will be generated are:

- SIGRUN: Reference integration based on requirements and needs highlighted by end users and participants of the Consortium.
- KARA: Block intended for technologies and equipment
- HERJA: Procedures and operations
- EIR: Collaboration and training

Disasters require rapid adoption to the circumstances. They differ widely from a closed process in which all the inputs and outputs of the process are known. Therefore, a standard methodology is not the same as in other areas and a more agile process is required.

² [About - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://europa.eu)

3.1. OODA Cycle - Introduction

The appearance of disasters and emergencies can have a natural origin that is difficult to detect beforehand, either due to natural or man-made causes. These challenges are constant in the military environment, for this reason the OODA decision-making tool was born and developed, since it was created by Colonel John Boyd of the United States Air Force based on his experience in combat and training of pilots. VALKYRIES uses OODA as a decision-making tool in uncertain and chaotic environments in a combined framework of harmonization and validation. It presents a dynamic continuous improvement cycle applicable to any business area and its characteristic is rapid decision-making when a problem appears on the horizon, allowing the use of the latest technological advances as solutions.

OODA tool is applied directly to command and control, which it could be a process, a tool, or a device that executes four basic tasks sequentially and repetitively: observation or data collection, elaboration of information or orientation, then taking or it helps to make a decision and in the end it is executed or acted upon. The treatment of command and control together with the OODA tool is to try to prevent, modify or interfere with the OODA cycle causing any disaster, for example, an electromagnetic countermeasure or a computer virus. According to Boyd, the success of the tool will be greater the faster its OODA cycle is completed, since it means a greater update, it adapts better to the environment and/or present adversities, cancelling their effect. To achieve success, the least possible friction must be pursued internally, that is, between all the participants in the tasks at each stage of the cycle. For this, it is a requirement that everyone has perfect knowledge of the objectives of leadership and the alignment of each participant with this and the objectives set. This shared vision guarantees coherence between strategy, operations and tasks that are carried out to achieve the objectives³.

Figure 2 - OODA loop

OODA is made up of four phases that continuously within an identified context, both internal and external, and dynamic, which works continuously, updating the result for optimal decision-making at all times.

- Observation: Deep acquisition of knowledge and preliminary information.
- Orientation: Through data analysis, the best hypothetical approximation is reached to address the gaps discovered and materialize the opportunities.

³ <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/download/articulo/4604097.pdf>

- Decision: Selection of the most appropriate harmonization path and it is applied within the integration.
- Action: Display, evaluate and contrast the assumed hypothesis based on the analysis of the information.

3.2. OODA vs popular continuous improvement tools

Over the years, overcoming obstacles in a global and dynamic environment, it has created a multitude of decision-making tools and continuous improvement tools that help achieve success and the best solutions in all kinds of activities.

Some of the most popular decision-making tools are SWOT analysis, Pareto diagrams, decision tree, Ishikawa diagram, or the recent Big Data. Each one presents some characteristics. Ishikawa diagram or fish tail shows the possible causes of a specific event so that by solving the root cause a problem can be solved. The decision tree is a flowchart that illustrates the results of different options in the form of a tree. Big Data uses a huge amount of data that, after analysis, generates results to facilitate decision-making.

On the other hand, the best-known continuous improvement tools are PDCA, EFQM or Six Sigma. They are methodologies that seek to achieve better and better results continuously using parallel techniques.

OODA presents some benefits:

- Quick and simple decision-making without the need for iterative elaboration of a complete cycle like other continuous improvement tools
- To provide transparency between organizations and awareness of the context by having a constant review process in all phases and among all participants.
- Greater agility in the review of all phases of the improvement cycle allows for continuous improvement and immediate correction of deviations, maintaining an optimal level in the quality of the output of the processes.
- Dynamic behaviour of each of the phases compared to other continuous improvement methodologies, because traditionally the analysis is done on a consolidated or stable photo while the OODA tool works dynamically analysing different hypotheses and generating adapted solutions.
- To work in environments with low certainty.

4. Objectives

The main objective of the deliverable is to expose the harmonisation framework applied in Valkyries. In order to do so, it is necessary to understand the needs of the project, of a cross-border disaster and the specific need. Finally, the methodology will be adapted to the process by developing a framework.

The secondary objectives of this framework harmonization are:

- Aligning harmonisation requirements with the project
- Aligning project needs with the harmonisation methodology
- Enable other European projects to use the harmonization framework and its methodology.

4.1. Requirements traceability matrix

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	Deliverables	Compliance	Output
REQ_COM_T2.4_4	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	D2.4 D2.6 D2.12	REQUIRED	Framework developed in this document. Paper published as common reference point for discussion.

Table 1 – Requirements traceability matrix

5. OODA protocol

Valkyries' global vision encompasses four main levels of action inspired by the OODA cycle under a combined framework of harmonization and validation. For the transfer of the OODA concept to Valkyries. Observation with the acquisition of previous knowledge and information will be identified (gaps and opportunities will be identified between regulatory frameworks, international, national and local standards, as well as operational procedures. Will be accounted the needs of the different stakeholders. A map of opportunities for first aid and those innovations of any nature with high disruptive potential will be integrated into it.). Orient will be the reasons for the best hypothetical approaches to address the identified gaps and realize the opportunities (a harmonization framework will be established taking into account the regulatory implications on certain reference models and creating / adapting established and selected criteria among existing standards). Decide stage consists of selecting the most appropriate harmonization pathways and applying them to a reference integration (some of them will be technologies and equipment, capacity for interoperability, collaboration and training, and the development of procedures and operations). Finally, Act consists of deploying, evaluating and confirming the assumed hypothesis based on analytical and empirical results (assumed criteria will be confirmed. Border demonstrations are carried out for verification and validation under an evaluation methodology. Also, field notes and recommendations will be recognised).

Figure 3 - Valkyries OODA loop

The VALKYRIES Consortium hypothesis on potential OODA under the following core statements:

Fast and efficient reaction against disruptions and non-EU pre-standardisation actions. The OODA tool stands as suitable for any business in terms of quick decision-making in the face of any upcoming external challenge to maintain an optimal response to any event. It is of special interest with the appearance of new technological and computer solutions and those initiatives born from sharing information and online experience between entities of different nature and location but covered by common objectives.

Harmonisation supported by Divergent and Future Thinking mechanism. Convergent thinking consists of giving a specific solution to a specific problem, on the other hand, divergent thinking analyses the situation to assess different options and execute the optimal one or the one with the highest value in a complementary way, future thinking tries to analyse the possible changes in the future between various variable parameters. This unique conjunction within a multidisciplinary commission of experts allows the generation of different scenarios and hypotheses to achieve the optimal ones via a convergence of possible alternatives within a context of high variability or uncertainty.

Flexibility, usability and most effective stakeholder engagement. A feature of the OODA loop is the ability to generate small OODA loops that work towards a larger purpose. These small OODAs can converge aided by standardization and normalization by different groups and sources of information while dynamically impacting other OODAs. It is characteristic to have cycles that overlap in time and objective to reach the optimum, since the source of information and objectives are reviewed, under certain hypotheses.

Speed-up and agile rational-comprehensive decision-making. Taking solutions for major crises involves analysing the vertical and horizontal implications and their consequences at all levels, from the strategic to the field operation.

It is necessary to carry out a harmonization taking into account their ability to adapt, time and economic resources involved from their decision to deployment. The OODA-based approach tries to provide continuous flexibility in decision-making.

Deployable and applicable at capability thorough development life cycle. The harmonization through OODA developed by Valkyries allows obtaining EMS solutions from design, integration and validation. This generates a tool for obtaining other solutions in the future and adapting them to the European market under the highest-level standards and adapted to the identified needs and requirements.

The lack of harmonization and inefficient regulation represent a high cost in international initiatives. Any technological change, the appearance of new and unique solutions, pose a challenge in the face of the difficulties of cross-border, between different sectors and different hierarchy operation. This is observed when supervising compliance with regulatory requirements and the application framework for cross-border operations, requiring a high effort to comply.

The purpose and objective of the harmonization is to create, comply with and validate a methodology based on the OODA for rapid and efficient response to the appearance of novel technological solutions by the first responders related to emerging technologies, procedures and collaborative environments. Carrying out decision-making in a rational manner under the convergent-divergent function and future thinking will allow adaptation to the particularities of the different sectors involved, transversal operation, usefulness and acceptance of the stakeholders involved in the harmonization process. The methodology will take into account all the relevant areas such as the political, economic, military, social, business, health, among others, and their possible combinations between them to analyse the final impact on all of them and on the final solution. To achieve success, various use cases will be developed where gaps and opportunities will have been identified to carry out a reference integration to generate guidelines, field notes and lessons learned as a result.

6. Valkyries information flows

The Valkyries organisation chart defines a relationship between the different work packages.

Valkyries is composed of seven work packages:

Work package 1 is the operational and technical project management part of the project with contractual, financial, legal, technical, ethical and administrative components. It also aims at securing the work plan, decision-making, technical coordination, data management and quality assurance support it.

The work package 2 provides specifications and requirements to be taken into account in the project life cycle. It provides a common frame of reference. This work package guides the rest of the project. From the task requirements, the harmonisation methodology to the overarching architecture.

Work package 3 defines the Valkyries ecosystem. In ethical-legal and societal terms. This work package guides the rest of the project: from ethical-legal aspects to data protection, standards and certification.

On the other hand, the technological work packages. These work packages are the ones that will concentrate the more technical work to provide more inputs and outputs to the project system.

- WP4: Equipment and ICT enablers for First Aid Responses
- WP5: Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responses
- WP6: Cooperation, Education and Training for First Aid Responses

The work package 7 represents the integration reference in the platform (SIGRUN). Also in the evaluation and demonstration through the use cases. Tests will be carried out on what has been provided in the project in this final stage.

Each work package produces inputs and outputs that affect other work packages.

Work packages have needs (inputs) that must be solved by others producing a guideline or recommendation (output). This process within work packages occurs with OODA loops.

6.1. OODA protocol in Valkyries tasks

In the following “*Figure 4 - Valkyries information flows*” can be seen the requirement relationships of the work packages

Figure 4 - Valkyries information flows

To explain how this works, we will explain an OODA cycle for a sample task within each of the harmonisation processes.

Task: Technological work packages do not know how to manage patient information in accordance with data protection.

Observe: The need for first responders is observed.

Orient: The decision process is oriented

Decide: The most appropriate option for managing the data is decided.

Act: The output is provided to the other work package

7. OODA protocol in Valkyries harmonization process

As discussed above, the more OODA cycles are run and the faster they are run, the better the result.

Therefore, the OODA cycle should contain simple problem solving. These problems should contain little information with few inputs and outputs so that they can be solved quickly. Large needs are broken down into small problems in order to quickly make decisions.

These small decisions are framed within the processes within each project task.

Each of the project tasks follows the defined harmonisation process in which first information is gathered, then gaps and community are detected and finally suggestions or improvements are produced. Finally, the output of each task together with the other tasks and the synergies between them form the output of the project

Just as information flowed through the tasks and from there to the work packages, internal decisions are made within the tasks. The sum of these small steps produces the harmonisation process, which is one of the steps of harmonisation.

7.1. Valkyries harmonization process

Figure 5 - Valkyries harmonisation process

The diagram above shows how the process of harmonisation of Valkyries has been carried out.

It has been a process tailor-made for the project and has been adjusted to the needs of the project at each stage.

It is necessary to remember that in this deliverable "harmonisation framework" and specifically in this point, the methodology followed in the project, the tasks elaborated to select the priorities and the pre-harmonisation in these points will be explained. Neither partial nor final results are shown. The results are part of the deliverable D2.12 "Harmonization and Standardization Reports"

There are clearly differentiated stages that have provided the outputs to start the next stage, which are described below:

7.1.1. Existing state-of-the-art

In the initial stage of the project the partners discussed the state of the art of the topics within the scope of the project.

The experts within the consortium provided their expertise to detect the current state of the art. The consortium partners are end-users or have a direct relationship with end-users and have therefore studied the current state of the art. This has been done in two sub-tasks.

Legal standard identification

In this task, information affecting specific sectors or countries has been collected.

All the standards related to the project must be collected and all the standards that directly affects VALYRIES in the Use Cases (UC) must be collected too.

This includes process maps, ISO and BSA standards, SOPs, regional ordinances, country laws, cooperation between countries, civil-military collaboration, European standards, GPR in companies and countries...

All of them organised by use case countries and/or sector.

Pre-identification of gaps

In this task, partners collect previously identified gaps and commonalities. Some data, such as gaps and commonalities, were identified prior to the meetings with the partners. This information comes not only from the partners' experience but also from an in-depth study of the literature and previous projects on these gaps and commonalities.

7.1.2. Gaps and opportunities identification

In this block the project looked for gaps between what the final respondents wanted, and the state of the art can provide. Improvements could be implemented, and pre-standardisation opportunities were proposed. To this end, the following tasks were carried out.

Identify required capabilities

Based on the current state of the art, the partners identified the capabilities required by end-users to successfully carry out the emergency.

Gaps

The leaders of the technology work packages and their tasks, analysed the requirements of the first responders and the level of technology was in this aspect. A lot of gaps was detected between what the first responders needed and what the current state of the art was.

The partners analysed the pre-identification of gaps made by the bibliographic references and experience of the partners and included it in the results.

A large number of gaps arose from each of the tasks in the technology work packages.

Opportunities

The project has detected a large number of harmonization needs or gaps. In the next step the project proposed solutions to these gaps called opportunities. The opportunities could provide a solution to one or more gaps. Resulting in fewer opportunities than gaps.

7.1.3. Suggestion and improvements

Prioritisation of opportunities

The project needed to prioritize the opportunities to find the best ones. However, a very large number of opportunities were provided, some of them were common to each other. It was too

large an amount to be evaluated, it was not manageable. If the consortium had asked for feedback from experts and stakeholders on this large number of opportunities, we would not have received a response.

It was therefore decided to group these opportunities together so that Valkyries researchers could work to catalogue, taxonomically homogenize, organize, evaluate similarities and differences, and finally group the individual opportunities.

Taxonomy

To detect similar opportunities, it was decided to unify criteria using the taxonomy tool created in task T2.2.

Task T2.2 aims to provide a unified glossary and a map of joint terminologies and semantic representations focused on the specificities of cross-sectoral, cross-border and cross-hierarchical action against European multi-victim disasters.

The objective is to support the harmonization, pre-standardization and standardization efforts of first responders in disasters. Deliverable D2.2 has been based on the proposal, debate, discussion and consensus of the different terms, and has been kept alive during the whole life cycle of the Project, serving as a constant reference for the researchers in their work and in the drafting of the respective deliverables. A website tool has also been developed to consult which specific term the words refer to.

Following this consensus, the researchers carried out a review of the terminology used in relation to the statements and contents of the opportunities detected in order to homogenize them. This facilitated not only the grouping of similar opportunities, but also the study of interdependencies between related opportunities inside and outside the WP, a fundamental aspect in the analysis, prioritization and roadmap for the evolution and adoption of new common practices and procedures for first responder responses in the EU environment.

Clustering of opportunities

In the previous stages of the project, a huge effort was made, and a great number of opportunities were identified in the three technological WP, some of them very similar.

The grouping of these opportunities has been done within each WP but transcending the initial organization of the project in tasks. In fact, this process has been carried out considering aspects related to methodology, objective, recipients, etc. independently of the WP task to which each individual opportunity was initially assigned.

This methodology has been considered not only convenient, but necessary to reflect the reality of the MCI and disaster response EU landscape and to fully explain the scope, impact and complexity of the clustered opportunities analysed.

The decision of reorganization allows an agile and efficient progress within each clustered opportunity, did not alter the initial distribution of the efforts committed by the investigators in each of the WPs tasks.

In conclusion, creating these opportunity groups was necessary, and it has also allowed to improve some aspects such as horizontality and to reduce to a handy amount which allows a detailed assessment to be made.

The reduction in the number of opportunities since the grouping has been 67%.

Opportunities analysis and prioritisation

Once the clusters of opportunities had been created, it was necessary to analyse them to prioritise the most relevant opportunities in each of the work packages.

Modified Delphi method

The project needed to reach a consensus on prioritising the opportunities identified to harmonise and test them in the use cases. The selected methodology was a Delphi method.

The Delphi method is a structured communication technique used to collect experts' opinion and knowledge on a particular topic or issue. It is a qualitative research method aims to reach a consensus among a group of experts by multiple rounds of surveys and feedback.

This method it is especially helpful in a situation where face-to-face meetings are difficult like this project

These are the steps of the method:

Figure 6 - Delphi method chart

1. Identify the topic. In that case the opportunities clusters.
2. Identify experts. In this case the consortium experts.
3. Create a questionnaire. Composed by several questions that we will see below
4. Inform how to use the questionnaire. In this case not all the consortium has the knowledge to answer all, so it was explained to them that if this was the case, they should leave it empty.
5. Distribute the questionnaire. This step must ensure the anonymity of data.
6. Analyse the responses
7. Start the loop again with more experts. (Outside of the actual scope)

Questionnaire

The main part of this method is the questionnaire. This time the opportunities have been analysed in two aspects **feasibility and impact**.

Feasibility refers to how viable or achievable it's the opportunity.

Impact refers to what is the effect or influence that the opportunity is expected.

The questionnaire consists of 13 questions, 7 for feasibility and 6 for impact. These questions will have a measurable score from 1 to 10. In such a way that the results are comparable. Moreover, each of the questions has a weight in the final score.

The questions within the feasibility group are focused to evaluated aspects such as the resources or capacities of the system, ethical-legal regulation, technological advances and implementation costs. As can be seen in the table below:

Feasibility determining factors evaluated	Contribution
Do the required training and learning processes present a high complexity to be implemented/operated?	8%
Is it possible to achieve a full operational harmonization for opportunities in less than a year for a first responder?	17%
Are there more than three first responders or entities involved to operate, consume or use directly this harmonization opportunity?	17%
Is there technology available to fulfill this opportunity?	17%
In terms of budget, how costly is it to develop, implement or operate this opportunity?	17%
How easy to implement in terms of legislation, ethics, and human rights?	7%
How easy is to verify and validate this opportunity in the whole Valkyries proposal?	17%

Table 2 - Feasibility questions

The questions within the impact group are focused to evaluate aspects such as the objective and the target stakeholders for whom it is proposed, or what is expected to happen in the end. As can be seen in the table below:

Impact determining factors evaluated	Contribution
Is there any environmental/social impact/risk when deploying?	33%
How reusable is across different regions, actors, and scenarios?	14%
Does the impact expected save lives or reduce casualties directly?	14%
Does the expected impact reduce the time to act?	13%
Does the expected impact reduce the risk of mistakes or rework?	13%
Is the expected impact useful to learn for next actuaciones?	13%

Table 3 - Impact questions

Matrix

With the answers to the questions and the appropriate weighting, a score will be obtained for each group. One for feasibility and one for impact. In this way, the opportunity can be placed in a matrix format.

The scores have been used as coordinates that replace the opportunity and locate the opportunity in the matrix. This can identify the opportunities with the best relation.

In the following image you can see the matrix with the x-axis representing feasibility and the y-axis representing impact. The matrix has been divided into four parts. Depending on the result obtained.

Figure 7 - Feasibility/Impact matrix

The result of the analysis in each case would fall into one of the following 4 combinations:

- **Low feasibility / Low impact (THANKLESS TASKS):** these are initiatives that are low recommended because they will not be significant for the desired changes in the system. The realization of these initiatives involves a high degree of difficulty for the implementation and the result will not bring a significant improvement.
- **High feasibility / Low impact (FILL-INS):** these are initiatives that can be implemented quickly and in the short term, but the effect they will have on the desired changes will be marginal and insignificant.
- **Low feasibility / High impact (MAJOR PROYECTS):** these are ideas, often disruptive, that are complex to execute. They may require further analysis or follow-up to assess their priority, degree of impact, risks involved in implementing them (or not implementing them), etc.
- **High feasibility / High impact (QUICK WINS):** these are initiatives that can be implemented and executed relatively easily in a short time. They are very valuable because they can generate a significant change in the system.

After completing the questionnaire, assess each of the opportunities and place them in the matrix. The project prioritises and selects the opportunities located at the top and left, looking for quick wins.

The number of opportunities is prioritised and reduced by 80% leaving a number of opportunities that the project has the capacity to implement in the use cases.

Interdependences

As an interdependence, we consider "the condition of two or more things depending on each other".

In the harmonisation process, there are dependencies, so that until one condition is met, the other cannot begin. These interdependences are analysed in this section, both inside and outside the work package. This analysis has only been carried out for the opportunities selected

as the most relevant. Interdependencies are unidirectional, but it is common for them to affect each other simultaneously and become bidirectional.

Roadmaps

Once the opportunities have been selected and interdependencies have been identified, it was necessary to create a roadmap to harmonise the selected opportunities. A schedule is needed for the achievement of implementing the opportunity.

For the implementation of these opportunities there are some common facts that every new opportunity must go through.

Some of these steps are a demo, several scientific publications, evaluation of the technologies, define consensus in a country, define consensus in EU, final standardisation. Yet each opportunity will need specific roadmap steps to be implemented.

SWOT analysis

After the roadmap of each of the opportunities, it is necessary to analyse them in depth. It is necessary to identify what it needs would cover, is there anything that make impossible the implementation or another more promising opportunity. To analyse these scenarios a SWOT analysis has been proposed.

SWOT analysis is a technique widely used in quality and in business to analyse a situation in order to make the right strategic decisions.

It is a systematic approach that facilitates analysis by distinguishing between the pros and cons of both the external and internal environment. In this way, 4 areas are defined which correspond to the acronym SWOT:

- **Strengths:** They bring together the set of internal resources, positions of power and any type of competitive advantage specific to the agent under study.
- **Weaknesses:** These are the aspects that limit the development capacity of the agent under study, due to its internal characteristics.
- **Opportunities:** These are any factors external to the agent under study that favour its development or offer the possibility of implementing improvements.
- **Threats:** These are all the external factors that could prevent the implementation of a strategy or jeopardise the viability of a proposal.

It can be represented graphically in 4 quadrants:

Figure 8 – SWOT chart

7.1.4. Use case testing

The selected opportunities have been tested in the use cases of the project and in the developed tools.

Not all opportunities have not been tested on all use cases and tools but have been divided by the scope of both and the availability of partners.

This has been the final evaluation of each of the opportunities. The lessons learned from the tests may have generated opportunities for pre-harmonization, proposals for common procedures or prioritized standards. It is expected that the results can be used as a basis for each of the prioritized opportunities to be a project in its own right for harmonization and integration into the European framework

8. Harmonization's outs

The opportunities have been evaluated in the use cases with a harmonized report in which the parameters have been considered:

- Date and location
- Participants
- Description
- Execution
- Analysis and results
- History of corrective measures
- Lessons learned
- Quality
- End-user feedback
- Result

The final results of the Use Cases are very extensive, so to see the detail it is necessary to refer to the deliverables below:

- D7.5: Report of the use case: Spain-Portugal
- D7.6: Report of the use case: Slovakia-Italy
- D7.7: Report of the use case: Bulgaria-Greece
- D7.8: Report of the use case: Norway-Netherlands

9. Annex A – Glossary

Acronym	Description
BSI	British Standards Institution
CEM	Copernicus Emergency Management Service
C&C	Command and Control
DRMKC	Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EFQM	European Foundation for Quality Management
EIOS	Epidemic Intelligence from Open Sources
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
EU	European Union
FAV	First Aid Vehicles
FMS	Fleet Management System
FRS	Fire and Rescue Service
GA	Grant Agreement
GCRI	Global Conflict Risk Index
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information System
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MCD	Minimum Common Data
MDS	Minimum Data Set
MCDT1	MCD Primary Triage
MCDT2	MCD Secondary Triage
MCI	Multi Casualty Incident
MS	Member States
OODA	Observe – Orient – Decide - Act
PDCA	Plan – Do – Check - Act
SMDRM	Social Media-Driven Disaster Risk Management
SOPs	Standard Operational Procedures
SWOT	Strengths – Weaknesses – Opportunities – Threats
UC	Use Case
UCPM	Union Civil Protection Mechanisms
VOSTs	Virtual Operation Support Teams
WP	Advanced Command Post

Table 4 - Glossary